

Enhancing a Distributed Electric Propulsion Configuration Aircraft Design with a Multidisciplinary Analysis and Optimization Approach

D. Granata¹, S. Mancini², A. Mateo-Gabin³, A. Zanotti¹

¹ Politecnico di Milano, Dipartimento di Scienze e Tecnologie Aerospaziali, via La Masa 34, 20156, Milan, Italy.

² Airbus Defence and Space GmbH, Rechliner Str., 85077 Manching, Germany.

³ Airbus Defence and Space SAU, Paseo John Lennon, 28906 Getafe, Spain.

ABSTRACT

The aviation industry's current push to reduce emissions has sparked interest in highly integrated hybrid-electric aircraft. Distributed electric propulsion (DEP) systems show promise in helping achieve these emission targets. However, the high integration of aircraft structure, aerodynamics, propulsion, and power supply in hybrid-electric DEP systems necessitates a multidisciplinary analysis approach to identify robust design trade-offs. This paper presents an extended multidisciplinary design and simulation environment applied to a hybrid-electric regional aircraft configuration. The traditional aerostructural optimization process has been enhanced to include aircraft stability and control aspects. To manage computational costs while balancing design and optimization trade-offs, a multi-fidelity approach is employed, utilizing both full-order and reduced-order models. Additionally, a model has been integrated to assess the flying qualities and aerodynamic characteristics of the aircraft within the multidisciplinary framework. The results demonstrate that the design optimization of the considered aircraft configuration is significantly influenced by constraints related to aircraft stability and control.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing interest on directing technological development towards environmentally compliant solutions. This effort includes optimizing existing traditional technologies to maintain, or even enhance, performance while simultaneously minimizing environmental impact. In this context, the aerospace sector has also seen a strong push toward the development of low-emission technologies.

Within regional aviation, there has also been growing interest in reducing emissions while maximizing performance. Within the Clean Aviation framework, the Hybrid-Electric Regional Architecture (HERA) project has been developed to investigate and optimize the concept of a regional aircraft integrating hybrid-electric technologies. HERA aims to identify and assess viable aircraft-level architectures capable of meeting the -50% greenhouse gas (GHG) emission target outlined in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). With a capacity of approximately 50–100 seats and a range suited to routes under 500 km, the aircraft is expected to enter into service by the 2040s. It will be compatible with multi-modal transportation frameworks and powered by hybrid-electric

systems combining batteries or fuel cells with Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) or hydrogen combustion. This architecture is expected to reduce emissions by up to 90% while fully complying with ICAO noise regulations. Figure 1 shows a conceptual representation of the HERA aircraft.

Figure 1. HERA conceptual design representation.

One of HERA's use cases distinguishing features is the use of distributed electric propulsion (DEP), where multiple propellers, both hybrid and electric, are placed along the wing span. This setup not only can possibly enhance aerodynamic performance by modifying the pressure distribution across the wing, but also improves safety through propulsion redundancy. However, implementing such a configuration introduces significant engineering challenges. Important among these are the aerodynamic interactions between the wing and propellers, which strongly affect the wing's performance and overall efficiency.

Numerous studies in literature have highlighted the non-

Copyright Statement

The authors confirm that they, and/or their company or organization, hold copyright on all of the original material included in this paper. The authors also confirm that they have obtained permission, from the copyright holder of any third-party material included in this paper, to publish it as part of their paper. The authors confirm that they give permission, or have obtained permission from the copyright holder of this paper, for the publication and distribution of this paper as part of the ERF proceedings or as individual offprints from the proceedings and for inclusion in a freely accessible web-based repository.

negligible effects of propeller–wing and propeller–propeller interactions on the aerodynamic performance of innovative aircraft configurations, as a function of the design variables. These effects include rotor-induced downwash, variations in local dynamic pressure, and upwash/downwash regions that depend on the rotor’s rotation direction, all of which significantly alter the wing’s load distribution, while at the same time, the wing induces a thickness and a doublet induced velocity along the propeller disk (Ref. 1). At Politecnico di Milano, extensive research has been conducted to experimentally and numerically to quantify these aerodynamic interactions with respect to different design variables (Refs. 2–4). Geng et al. also studied the performance implications of wingtip-mounted and distributed propellers using the HMB3 CFD solver (Ref. 5). Their results indicate that these interactions consistently influence both propeller and wing performance, and thus must be carefully accounted for during the design phase.

Additionally, hybrid-electric configurations like HERA require a highly multidisciplinary design approach from the earliest stages. This includes not only aerodynamic and structural considerations but also propulsion, acoustics and safety/certification factors.

A multidisciplinary framework, indeed, enables the use of discipline-based objective functions such as the aircraft aerodynamic efficiency, and the wing structural mass, quantities that are directly linked to the overall manufacturing and operational costs of the aircraft. Optimizing these different quantities is essential to ensure affordability, a critical success factor for new aerospace products. Moreover, within the design of new DEP configurations, a multidisciplinary approach is essential also because design variables are shared across multiple disciplines.

Affordability is further influenced by certification requirements and social acceptance. Certification is often among the most costly and time-consuming phases of aircraft development, and meeting safety standards involves extensive testing, validation, and sometimes multiple design iterations driven by regulatory feedback. These iterations raise development costs and delay the time-to-market of new aircrafts, and therefore taking certification constraints into account during the preliminary design phase can lead to significant advantages in terms of the affordability of the new configuration.

Given the complexity of the design space, Multidisciplinary Design Optimization (MDO) is a well-suited approach for the development of such integrated aircraft. Several works in literature have applied MDO in the early stages of aircraft development to explore feasible and compliant design regions. Hendricks et al. (Ref. 6) proposed an MDO environment for preliminary eVTOL configurations, coupling different subsystems in the MDO formulation. Petersson et al. (Ref. 7) highlighted how feasible designs can be achieved under industrial constraints using MDO in both preliminary and conceptual phases, significantly reducing redesign costs. In this work, he presented MDO results for transonic swept-wing aerostructural design and fuselage optimization. Gazaix et al.

applied MDO to the aerostructural design of an aircraft engine pylon, highlighting the multidisciplinary of the problem and the difficulties of integrating high-fidelity simulations to predict pylon loads (Ref. 8).

For the purpose of efficiently populating the design space reduced order models can be considered. Frink et al. (Ref. 9), instead employed surrogate models to represent the aerodynamic behavior of the SACCON configuration developed by the NATO RTO. Using a Kriging-based surrogate model built from stability and control derivatives, he accurately predicted dynamic responses with significantly lower computational cost. Granata et al. (Ref. 10) proposed an alternative method using the DUST aerodynamic solver to simulate multi-frequency oscillatory motions and estimating the complete set of stability derivatives. This enables comprehensive flight mechanics modeling and the inclusion of flying qualities constraints within the MDO framework.

The objective of the present work is therefore to perform a multi-disciplinary analysis based on detailed aerodynamic analysis of the one of HERA aircraft configuration, namely the Use Case B(UCB), with a focus on wing–propeller interaction effects and their impact on design optimization. We investigate the usage of a multi-fidelity approach in that some of the models, i.e. aerodynamic and stability and control model, are also instantiated as surrogates of the corresponding full-order model. The multidisciplinary optimization environment is expanded to incorporate flying qualities constraints into the optimization loop. These are evaluated using the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver *DUST* and constraints are created according to guidelines from certification requirements. The aircraft trim is also included in the loop. This framework allows the preliminary design phase to deliver a compliant, optimized configuration, thus potentially reducing the need for costly redesigns in later development stages. Finally, this study also evaluates the use of surrogate models for optimization and compares different sampling and optimization algorithms, such as MDF and Bi-Level strategies. The developed framework integrates the *DUST* (Ref. 11) aerodynamic solver with the open-source optimizer *GEMSEO* (Ref. 12):

- *DUST* is a mid-fidelity aerodynamic computational tool, developed by Politecnico di Milano, which provides a fast and reliable simulation environment for complex aircraft configurations, such as eVTOL aircraft, tiltrotors and DEP configurations. *DUST* is an open-source code released under the MIT license, integrating different aerodynamic models for solid bodies, thick surface panels, thin vortex lattice elements, and lifting line elements. Additionally, a Vortex Particle Method (VPM) is implemented for wake modeling, offering a stable Lagrangian representation of free-vorticity flow fields. This feature makes it particularly suitable for numerical simulations of configurations with strong aerodynamic interactions. Details regarding the solver’s mathematical formulation can be found in (Ref. 13). In this study, *DUST* is used to develop the aerodynamic model of the HERA aircraft and to perform aerodynamic analyses, including

polar curves, stability and control assessments, and wake interaction aerodynamics studies.

- *GEMSEO* (Generic Engine for Multidisciplinary Scenarios, Exploration, and Optimization) is an open-source Python-based software designed to automate multidisciplinary processes, particularly those related to Multidisciplinary Design Optimization (MDO). It offers a variety of MDO formulations and is built on NumPy, SciPy, and Matplotlib, incorporating algorithms for coupling, design of experiments, linear problems, optimization, machine learning, surrogate modeling, uncertainty quantification, and visualization. *GEMSEO* can be integrated into simulation platforms or used as a standalone tool. It supports Python, MATLAB, Scilab scripts, Excel spreadsheets, and other executable codes callable from Python.

NUMERICAL METHODOLOGY

HERA DUST Numerical Model

This section describes the aerodynamic model built in DUST, developed for HERA. This model, cross-validated against a RANS solution of the TAU software based on the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model (Ref. 14), was employed for the aerodynamic analysis of the configuration and a reduced vortex-lattice version is used in the MDO loop for configuration optimization. Specifically, DUST was employed for load estimation and for evaluating aerodynamic stability properties, which were used to compute the flying qualities of the aircraft. For these reasons, the DUST model represents an important element of the present work and is described in detail in the following.

The HERA configuration features a main wing and a T-tail horizontal stabilizer. It also incorporates an innovative hybrid-electric propulsion system, with propulsion units mounted on the main wing. In particular, each wing hosts one hybrid rotor placed near the wing root, and two smaller electric rotors positioned farther outboard. Depending on the flight regime, the thrust distribution between the hybrid and electric motors varies.

Figure 2 shows the aerodynamic model of HERA built in DUST, along with the associated mesh, which consists of 14460 elements. The main wing, horizontal tail, and vertical tail were parametrically generated in DUST and modeled using surface panel elements. A complete analytical description of the formulation for these implicit elements can be found in Ref. (Ref. 13). The full parametrization of these components was chosen due to its suitability for use within a multidisciplinary optimizer. Control surfaces were also modeled on each of these lifting surfaces, leveraging the built-in capabilities provided in DUST (Ref. 15). The fuselage is likewise represented with surface panel elements. Its mesh was generated externally using a MATLAB script, based on the parametric fuselage modeling formulation described in (Ref. 16). The structured mesh is then imported into DUST using raw point

and connectivity files. The rotors, on the other hand, were modeled using lifting-line elements (Ref. 13), which enable solving an explicit problem by evaluating blade loads through the use of C81 lookup tables. The lookup tables for both hybrid and electric rotor blades were generated using the open-source tool NeuralFoil by Peter Sharpe (Ref. 17), a rapid airfoil analysis tool based on a hybrid approach that combines physics-informed machine learning techniques with analytical models, trained on tens of millions of XFOIL simulations.

Figure 2. HERA DUST Aerodynamic model and mesh (baseline configuration).

Table 1 reports the number of elements in the mesh for each component of the model. The mesh resolution was chosen following a convergence study for each part of the aerodynamic model, ensuring that load variation remained within 0.5%. For the static simulations, used both for validation and for assessing the aircraft’s static stability, a total simulation time of 0.3 seconds was chosen, with a time step of 0.001 seconds. For the dynamic simulations, the simulation time was set to 1 second, due to the need to capture the dynamic motions described in Ref. (Ref. 10).

Table 1. Aerodynamic mesh specifications (Vortex Lattice model in brackets)

Solver	N.Components	N.elements x comp.
Wing	1	9000 (600)
Tail	1	2080 (400)
Hybrid Rotor	2	232 (144)
Electric Rotor	4	116 (72)
Fuselage	1	2452 (/)
Total	/	14460 (1216)

Table 2 instead lists the aerodynamic conditions used for the multi-fidelity validation of the model against the TAU solver. For optimization purposes, only cruise flight conditions will be considered. Aerodynamic coefficients were computed by non-dimensionalizing with respect to dynamic pressure and the geometric properties of the aircraft.

The model described above was used to perform cross-

Table 2. Angle of Attack per Solver and Condition

Solver	Condition	Angle of Attack [°]
DUST	Cruise	0, 5, 10
TAU	Cruise	0, 5, 10

validation with a CFD model of HERA, specifically characterized by the presence of actuator disks for the modeling of the propellers. The actuator disks in the CFD model take as input the loads provided by DUST, ensuring that the validation of the wing loading is carried out under equal propeller thrust conditions. The focus of this part of the work is indeed on the accurate characterization of the loads acting on the wing, including those due to wing-propeller interaction, which is essential for the subsequent optimization of the configuration.

Following validation and aerodynamic analysis, the DUST model is then replaced with a lower-fidelity DUST model characterized by Vortex Lattice elements (Tab. 1 shows the mesh specification in brackets) instead of the more computationally expensive 3D surface panel elements. The Vortex Lattice model was correlated with the surface panel model, as will be shown in Figure 11, and then used in the MDO loop. This allowed for a computational cost speed-up of up to 10 times compared to the surface panel model, which was critical during the testing phase of the implemented code.

Multidisciplinary Optimization Framework

This section presents the multidisciplinary optimization environment developed and used in this work to perform MDO on the HERA configuration. The framework has been originally developed in previous works (Ref. 18) at Airbus Defence and Space and has been further extended and refined in the present study to achieve the objectives outlined in section . The following describes the developed environment and the logic behind the implementation of the tool, along with recent additions introduced in this work. The MDO framework is based on the need to couple various disciplines that reflect different physical aspects involved in the flight physics of the aircraft. In this regard, the open-source optimizer GEMSEO proves to be well-suited, as it is specifically designed to connect multiple disciplines. Through a customized library, it enables the communication between different design variables linked to various aircraft components. The framework itself is composed of several modules interfacing with GEMSEO and coordinated by an executable script that also includes the optimization logic, chosen by the user among the available strategies in GEMSEO.

- The assembly module acts as a descriptive layer that connects the flight environment (i.e., mission segment or flight condition under analysis) with the physical components of the aircraft. This module includes all the classes needed to define subsystems, introduced as objects with attributes (defining their properties) and methods (for operating on the physical components). For example, one

such class is Section, a dictionary containing all the information about each airfoil profile of a parametric Wing class (another object in the assembly). The definition and interconnection of these subsystems follow the CPACS format, ensuring proper handling of components linked by interaction constraints (e.g., geometrical dependencies). By chaining simpler elements, the full system is defined. Complex components can be nested and retain data relevant to their hierarchical level, for instance, a propeller composed of identical blades, each defined by sections placed according to chord and twist distribution, as illustrated in Fig. 3 .

Figure 3. Data structure of a propeller component.

- Disciplines represent independent physical models such as aerodynamics or structural analysis. To be integrated into the GEMSEO workflow, each discipline must expose an interface specifying its required input variables and the output it generates. In other words, each discipline is implemented as a dedicated module containing the classes needed to retrieve inputs from the assembly components and deliver pre-defined outputs compatible with GEMSEO. These outputs can then be used as objective functions or constraints in the optimization process. The disciplines developed and used in this work focus on the aero-structural optimization of HERA's main wing, also considering flying qualities constraints:

Aerodynamics: The aerodynamic module serves as the interface to the mid-fidelity aerodynamic code DUST. It takes input from the assembly module, thus having full knowledge of the aircraft components and flight conditions. With these inputs, the aerodynamic problem is uniquely defined in DUST, including parametric geometry generation (wings, fuselage, propeller) and flight conditions (freestream velocity, angle of attack and sideslip). Users may also select specific options such as simulation timestep, total simulated time, mesh resolution, number of wake panels, and vortex particles. Beyond static aerodynamics, the module implements subroutines for computing aerodynamic stability and control derivatives. These include static derivatives (evaluated via finite differences between two attitudes), dynamic stability derivatives (computed with the methods from (Ref. 10)), and control derivatives for aileron, elevator, and rudder, also evaluated using finite differences. Derivatives are used by the stability and control discipline for the reduced-order modeling of the vehicle. The final aerodynamic outputs include aerodynamic loads (lift, drag, thrust, moments) and all stability/control derivatives.

Structural Sizing: The structural sizing discipline aims at

sizing the primary wing structure, while the structure of the fuselage is kept constant as well as that of the tail plane. The model sizes the wing spars, stringers, ribs and panels by using spanwise aerodynamic loads, the weight and position of the engines. The structural sizing model defines the set of thicknesses that minimize the weight for each section using different criteria for each skin and web, maintaining a predefined reserve factor (RF) of 1.5 which are implemented in the Airbus in-house mid-fidelity structural sizing tool AMPET (Ref. 19) and more recently coupled by the in-house multidisciplinary framework built around GEMSEO (Ref. 20)

Weight and Balance: The Weight and Balance module handles the aggregation of mass properties of all aircraft components. Each component is assigned a mass, center of gravity, and inertia tensor, either user-defined or computed by another discipline (e.g., structural sizing for the wing). The module sums the masses, computes the global center of gravity, and calculates the total inertia tensor in body axes. This information is then used by the stability and control discipline.

Stability and Control: The Stability and Control module gathers aerodynamic derivatives and inertial data to compute three different kind of outputs: static margin (SM), flying qualities (based on the reduced formulation from (Ref. 21)), and, if desired, maneuvering time estimates based on control surface inputs and known damping/control derivatives and inertial properties. Generally speaking, this discipline provides essential metrics for assessing vehicle handling and stability.

The *Variable* class represents the final key element of the framework. It allows specific attributes to be flagged as optimization variables. Each variable is a simple structure storing a name, initial value, and optional bounds. Variables are defined in the main executable, and they are attached to the components of the assembly. Once attached to a component attribute, the optimizer can track and update it throughout the optimization.

Within GEMSEO, several MDO formulations are available to couple the MDA analysis and the optimization logic, such as the Multidisciplinary Feasible (MDF), which solves the coupled system at each optimization iteration ensuring feasibility; the Individual Discipline Feasible (IDF), which treats coupling variables as independent optimization variables with consistency constraints; and the Bi-Level formulation, which separates the problem into a lower-level disciplinary optimization and an upper-level coordination problem. Figure 4 illustrates a high-level diagram of the optimization process and interactions between the various components of the framework, using the MDF (Multidisciplinary Feasible) algorithm.

Surrogate modelling

The presented problem involves multiple disciplines and, as in the case of DUST, requires executing simulations from dedi-

cated solvers. During an optimization process, this becomes particularly onerous due to the need to repeatedly perform the simulation while varying design parameters and so computing the Jacobian matrix that supplies sensitivity information to the optimization algorithm (Fig. 4). This process results in significant computational costs.

To alleviate this issue, the adoption of surrogate models, constructed through Design of Experiment (DOE) approaches, has proven highly effective, as supported by recent literature (Ref. 22) (Ref. 23). A surrogate model approximates a given discipline as an explicit Multi-Input Multi-Output (MIMO) function of the design variables involved in the optimization (Ref. 24).

These models are built using DOE (Design of Experiment) approaches. A DOE approach can be divided into five significant steps.

- *Planning* The first step is the planning the experiment and so, the definition of the discipline, the design space and the constraints.
- *Sampling* The second step consists of selecting a sampling strategy to choose a set of meaningful points within the design space that will serve as inputs for evaluating the discipline. GEMSEO provides several sampling methods for this purpose, such as the FFS (Full Factorial Sampling), LHS (Latin Hypercube Sampling), and quasi-random sequences such as Sobol and Halton or simpler Monte Carlo.
- *Execution* The third step concerns the actual execution of the experiment, where the disciplinary solver is run on each of the sampled points selected in the previous phase, and the outputs of the discipline are stored.
- *Regression* The fourth step involves building the surrogate input/output model. This is done by training a regression model that captures the relationship between the design variables and the outputs of the discipline. GEMSEO supports various Machine Learning (ML) models for this task. Linear regression is often used for its simplicity and speed in capturing basic trends, while polynomial regression is useful for modeling nonlinear behavior. More advanced techniques include Gaussian Process Regression (GPR or Kriging), which provides both predictions and uncertainty estimates and is well-suited for smooth nonlinear functions. Radial Basis Function (RBF) regressor is also available and effective for scattered, nonlinear data.
- *Validation* Finally, in the fifth step, systematic simulations are performed at new design points that were not part of the initial sampling. The outputs predicted by the surrogate model are then compared with those obtained from the actual solver to assess the model's accuracy and generalization capability.

A dedicated module has been developed within the Multidisciplinary framework to create surrogate models via DOE

Figure 4. DUST-GEMSEO interface and optimization loop with Multidisciplinary Feasible (MDF) MDO formulation architecture.

approach. Each disciplinary block in Figure 4 is treated as a black box with its own input/output structure, and GEMSEO’s built-in algorithms are employed for both sampling and model fitting. When the surrogate option is activated, the original block is replaced by a MIMO surrogate that preserves the same I/O structure, effectively emulating the behavior of the underlying discipline with significantly reduced computational effort.

In the present work, the module was used to create surrogate models for the aerodynamic loads and stability discipline (see Fig. 4), which is characterized by the use of DUST. DUST samples are selected using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS), a statistical method for generating a near-random sample of parameter values from a multidimensional distribution and aims to spread the sample points more evenly across all possible values. Also, a Gaussian Process Regressor (GPR) is used to generate the surrogate models from the DOE points. GPR is a non-parametric Bayesian method used for regression tasks. It models the relationship between input and output variables by defining a probability distribution over functions.

RESULTS

This section addresses two main topics. The first concerns the validation of the DUST aerodynamic model against the RANS-based solutions of the TAU solver.

Firstly, the aerodynamic interaction between the wing and the propellers will be analyzed in terms of its effects on the wing loads, which are central to the configuration optimization process.

Then, the optimization will be carried out. This part is divided into three steps: the transition to a reduced vortex lattice model, the creation of surrogate models, and finally, the optimization process. The optimization process consists of two main phases: a trim optimization, aimed at identifying the steady-state cruise attitude using the MDO framework; and the actual optimization of the geometry and propeller placement under cruise trim conditions, considering constraints on stability derivatives and flying qualities. These last two phases could technically have been combined, as the developed MDO framework supports optimization with trim in the loop. However, they were separated for clarity, consistency, and to reduce the training cost of the surrogate model, which would have been more demanding in a coupled setup.

Aerodynamic analysis

This paragraph analyzes the cross-validation between the DUST model and the TAU CFD model, as well as the aerodynamic interaction effects between the wing and the propellers. Figure 5 shows a comparison of the pressure distribution between the DUST model on the left and the TAU model on the right. As previously discussed, the TAU model includes actuator disks to simulate the propellers, whereas DUST employs lifting line elements. The main goal of this phase is to observe the behavior of the two models and ensure that a consistent setup is being established. As shown in Figure 5 (a), for an angle of attack $\alpha = 0^\circ$, the correlation between the two aerodynamic solvers is good, although the CFD solver, likely due to the use of actuator disks and mesh dissipation, exhibits a more limited interaction effect on the wing. A similar observation can be made for Figure 5 (b), corresponding to $\alpha = 5^\circ$.

At $\alpha = 10^\circ$, it is evident that DUST predicts stronger interaction effects, as seen from the larger spanwise deviation of C_p . However, it fails to capture flow separation effects caused by the high angle of attack under cruise conditions. This separation leads to a reduction in aerodynamic load that the VPM solver is not able to accurately reproduce in this higher attitude of the aircraft.

Figure 5. Pressure coefficient distribution on the wing for DUST and TAU (CFD RANS) solutions (a) $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (b) $\alpha = 5^\circ$ (c) $\alpha = 10^\circ$

Figure 6 shows the chordwise distribution of C_p for angles of attack $\alpha = 0, 5, 10$, at two different spanwise sections: one located within the propeller wake (in-wake, $y/b = 0.2985$), and one outside the propeller wake (out-wake, $y/b = 0.9630$). It can be observed that for angles $\alpha = 0$ and 5 , there is excellent agreement between the models both in-wake and out-wake. However, for $\alpha = 10^\circ$, DUST accurately captures the out-wake section but fails in the in-wake region. This discrepancy is due to the fact that, in the in-wake region, the propeller wake induces an upwash and increases the dynamic pressure on the wing, triggering flow separation, an effect already visible in Figure 5. In Figure 6 (f), this separation manifests as a sudden drop in C_p , which results in a significant decrease in wing loading in the in-wake region.

Figure 7 shows the comparison between DUST and TAU in terms of the spanwise lift distribution for different angles of attack $\alpha = 0, 5, 10^\circ$. A slight overestimation of the load by TAU compared to DUST can be observed, but overall the correlation is excellent for the first two angles of attack, particularly in terms of the trend and the spanwise derivative of the load. At $\alpha = 10^\circ$, separation effects captured by the CFD solver become significant, leading to noticeable differences in the load distribution. In fact, DUST overestimates the load by approximately 10%, highlighting the limitations of the VPM solver at high angles of attack. It is important to note that

the largest discrepancy occurs around $y/b = 0.4$, where the wing-propeller interaction induces flow separation.

Similar considerations apply to the integral loads, shown in Figure 8 in terms of vertical force coefficient C_Z , longitudinal force coefficient C_X , and pitching moment coefficient C_m . In this representation, prior to the onset of stall at $\alpha = 10$, there is excellent agreement between the models, especially for the derivatives $C_{Z\alpha}$ and $C_{m\alpha}$ (i.e., the slope of the curve between 0° and 5°), which deviate by less than 1% from TAU results. These derivatives are crucial both for the computation of flying qualities (such as static margin and the frequencies and damping of the aircraft’s modes) and for the gradient-based optimization process.

Figure 9 (a) presents a DUST-only comparison between the “Clean” configuration, i.e., the wing without propellers, and the configuration with propellers, for the three angles of attack previously analyzed. The effects of wing-propeller interaction on the spanwise loads can be clearly observed, leading to a characteristic upwash-downwash dipole pattern in the induced velocity field. This results in local variations in angle of attack and loading when the propeller wake impinges on the wing. This phenomenon is consistently observed across all three angles of attack and leads to variations in the integral loads of up to 10%, highlighting the importance of accounting for aerodynamic interaction effects in the optimization process. Figure 9 (b) provides a visualization of the pressure coefficient (C_p) distribution over the wing, along with an iso-surface of vorticity based on the Q-criterion to represent the wake. This visualization reinforces the previously described effects: the main outcomes of the rotor-wing interaction are the increase in dynamic pressure, resulting in changes in C_p , and the presence of upwash and downwash caused by the propeller swirl, which is particularly pronounced for the hybrid rotor of HERA.

Trim optimization

This section addresses the solution of the longitudinal trim problem for the previously introduced HERA configuration. In this context, the developed MDO framework optimizer is used to carry out the trim of the aircraft. Here, the trim variables are treated as design variables subject to constraints. Table 3 outlines the definition of the problem, showing that the considered trim variables are the aircraft angle of attack, which primarily balances the vertical forces ($\sum F_Z$); the blade pitch of the hybrid and electric motors, which contribute to the longitudinal trim ($\sum F_X$) by acting on the thrust of the rotors to counterbalance drag; and the deflection of the elevator control surface, which mainly balances the pitching moment around the center of gravity ($\sum M_{Y_{CG}}$). A multidisciplinary approach remains necessary in this case, as the disciplines of aerodynamics and weight and balance are both involved. Additionally, since the number of trim variables exceeds the number of constraints, selecting different pitch values for the electric and hybrid propeller blades already provides insight into the optimal thrust split between the two propulsion types. Figure 10 shows instead the Extended Design Structure Matrix (xdsM)

Figure 6. Chordwise pressure coefficient distribution, non-dimensionalized with respect to the maximum value, for different angles of attack, inside (in-wake: $y/b = 0.31$) and outside (out-of-wake: $y/b = 0.96$) the propeller wake, DUST and TAU solutions.

Figure 7. Sectional lift load coefficient as a function of the wing spanwise coordinate, for different angle of attacks, DUST and TAU solutions.

of the trim problem, highlighting the input (vertical endings) and the output (horizontal) of each discipline.

Table 3. Trim Optimization problem definition

Trim Variables	Constraints	Objective
$-2^\circ < \alpha < 9^\circ$	$\sum F_X = 0$	L/D ratio
$40^\circ < \theta_{electric} < 60^\circ$	$\sum F_Z = 0$	
$40^\circ < \theta_{hybrid} < 60^\circ$	$\sum m_Y = 0$	
$-10^\circ < \delta_e < 10^\circ$		

Figure 11 shows the correlation between the DUST surface panel model, used in the previous section for the validation and analysis of wing, propeller aerodynamic interaction phenomena, and the DUST vortex lattice model, which is significantly less computationally expensive and therefore employed in the actual trim and MDO optimization process, including tests of optimizations without surrogate models. An excellent agreement can be observed between the two models in terms of sectional lift and drag, two of the most critical parameters for an aero-structural optimization with trim, where the focus lies on maximizing the lift-to-drag ratio (L/D). This is particularly true in the context of load distribution phenomena under wing-propeller interaction. Since the trends between the models are consistent, especially regarding the spanwise derivative of the load distribution, which is essential for optimization purposes, the vortex lattice model will be used for all subsequent analyses and considerations.

Figure 12 shows the training data for the surrogate model, the machine learning-based surrogate itself, and the validation points obtained from time-marching DUST simulations. The surrogate was trained using a Design of Experiment (DoE) approach with Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS), a sampling technique designed to generate a uniformly distributed set of points within a Latin hypercube, enabling efficient exploration of the design parameter space. A total of 120 training points were used, a value selected after a convergence study on the number of samples needed to achieve a coefficient of determination R^2 of 0.99. The regression model employed to build the surrogate is a Gaussian Process Regressor. For clarity and conciseness, only slices of the surrogate model are shown, illustrating the dependence of lift, drag, and pitching moment

Figure 8. Integral loads force X and Y and pitching moment coefficient, comparison between DUST and TAU as a function of the angle of attack.

Figure 9. (a) DUST Sectional lift load coefficient as a function of the spanwise coordinate, for different angles of attack. Comparison between clean wing configuration and installed-propeller configuration. (b) DUST pressure coefficient distribution and flow visualization with three-dimensional vorticity iso-contours of Q-criterion.

Figure 10. Extended Design Structure Matrix of the Trim problem.

Figure 11. Spanwise wing sectional lift and drag coefficient as a function of the spanwise coordinate, comparison between DUST Surface Panel elements solution and Vortex Lattice elements

on the angle of attack, as well as the total thrust of the vehicle as a function of the blade pitch angle of the hybrid motors. A strong correspondence can be observed between the machine learning model and the validation points obtained from time-marching simulations, particularly in terms of trends and derivatives/gradients, thus enabling the optimization process to be carried out in a manner consistent with the full-order model.

Figure 13 presents the results of the optimization: the trim condition, defined within a tolerance of 0.05 on the load coefficients, was achieved in 8 iterations. Figure 13 (a) shows the evolution of the total forces and moments acting on the aircraft across the optimization steps, confirming the convergence toward equilibrium. Figure 13 (b) compares the outcomes of the trim optimization when performed with and without the surrogate model. A strong correlation between the results is evident, demonstrating the validity and effectiveness of the DOE-based approach and the use of a surrogate model for optimization purposes. This strategy led to a reduction in computational time by approximately a factor of 10, even when accounting for the surrogate model’s training phase.

Multidisciplinary Design Optimization with Flying Qualities Constraints

This section presents the multidisciplinary optimization performed on the HERA configuration. Table 4 outlines the definition of the optimization problem, specifically identifying the design variables, constraints, and the objective function. Among the design variables, four are geometric: the wing kink point, the wing tip twist (which varies linearly from the airfoil at the kink point), the position of the electric propellers, which are translated along the wing span while maintaining a constant distance between them, as illustrated in Figure 14, and finally the horizontal tail plane scale, which is served to control the Flying Qualities (FQ) constraints. The remaining two design variables pertain to the wing structure: the area of the caps at the wing root and the area of the stringers. In addition to upper and lower bounds imposed on the design variables, the optimization includes constraints related to the aircraft’s longitudinal flying qualities. From the perspective of

static stability, a constraint is imposed on the aircraft’s static margin, defined as:

$$\text{S.M.} = \frac{x_{np} - x_{cg}}{\bar{c}} = \frac{-\bar{c}C_{m\alpha} - x_{cg}}{\bar{c}} = -\frac{C_{mCG\alpha}}{C_{ZCG\alpha}} \quad (1)$$

and required to lie between 5% and 30%, to ensure a good compromise between the aircraft’s stability and maneuverability. Additional constraints relate to the dynamic behavior of the aircraft, including the frequency of the short period mode, derived from a reduced-order model (Ref. 21) and the stability derivatives obtained using the methodology described in (Ref. 10). These constraints are defined as follows:

$$2\zeta_{sp}\omega_{sp} = -\left(\frac{M_q}{I_y} + \frac{Z_w}{m} + \frac{M_{\dot{w}}U_e}{I_y}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_{sp} = \sqrt{\frac{M_q}{I_y} + \frac{Z_w}{m} - M_w U_e} \quad (3)$$

$$\zeta_p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{C_D}{C_L} \quad (4)$$

The objective of the optimization is to maximize the aircraft’s range, defined by the Breguet range equation:

$$R = \frac{U_e}{c_s} \cdot \frac{L}{D} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{W_i}{W_f}\right) \quad (5)$$

which provides an optimal balance between maximizing the lift-to-drag ratio (L/D) and minimizing the wing mass.

Figure 15 shows the XDSM diagram of the optimization problem, highlighting the inputs (vertical edges) and outputs (horizontal edges) of each discipline. It is important to note that the MDAJacobi problem, associated with the design synthesis discipline, is only responsible for updating the aerodynamic derivatives vector. Specifically, the aerodynamic derivatives are computed in the aircraft’s global reference frame, while the design synthesis transforms them to the aircraft’s center of gravity, using the output provided by the weight and balance discipline. Additionally, the aerodynamic stability disciplines are treated separately, as each one produces a distinct output

Figure 12. Slices of Surrogate models for the aerodynamic discipline outputs. Training data (dependent on multiple variables), Surrogate data with fixed trim variables, validation point with fixed trim variables.

Figure 13. (a) Trim constraints evolution through the optimization (b) Trim optimization final results. Comparison between using the surrogate, and performing time-marching simulation through the optimization.

Table 4. MDO problem definition

Design Variables	Constraints	Objective
y_{kink}	$5 < S.M. < 35\%$	Range
θ_{tip}	$2.8 < \omega_{sp} < 3.2 \text{ rad/s}$	
y_{eprop}	$0.6 < \zeta_{sp} < 1.0$	
$A_{stringer@root}$	$\zeta_{phug} > 0.04$	
$A_{cap@root}$		
$htail \text{ scale}$		

Figure 14. MDO problem geometric design variables scheme.

and corresponds to a different simulation used to compute the derivatives, according to the motions defined in (Ref. 25).

Figure 16 shows the surrogate models generated by the developed framework, using Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) on 125 different design points, as a function of the design variables. Figure 16 presents the most representative slices of the resulting surrogate model, along with the training points, which show dispersion due to variability in the design parameters, and the validation points obtained from time-marching DUST simulations, with design parameters frozen to match the surrogate model slices. An excellent correlation can be observed between the surrogate model and the validation points, both for the aerodynamic loads on the wing, as a function of the design variables, and for the aircraft's stability properties, i.e., the neutral point computed by the DUST routine, and the dynamic stability derivatives obtained using the methodology described in (Ref. 10).

Figure 17 shows the results of the multidisciplinary optimization, specifically the resulting design variable values corresponding to the maximized objective function, while satisfying the constraints on the flying qualities. A good correlation can be observed between the results obtained with and without the surrogate model, highlighting the consistency of the DoE-based approach employed.

Figure 18 (a) shows the optimized configuration compared to the baseline configuration. Figure 18 (b) instead illustrates the distribution of the sectional lift coefficient as a function of the spanwise coordinate y , for the same total lift (the trim condition for the optimized configuration has been recalculated,

although it remains close to the initial value in terms of trim variables). The two distributions appear markedly different, due to the changes in the design variables, particularly the position of the propellers, which are responsible for the dipole-like effect observed in the load distribution. It's interesting to note that the optimized configuration is characterised by a loading distribution more similar to the elliptical one, demonstrating the advantage of using the electric propellers as a design variable.

Figure 19 shows the evolution of the constraint on the static margin of the aircraft, expressed as the percentage difference between the neutral point of the aircraft and the center of gravity, which are both varying within the optimization history. It is shown that the implemented framework can effectively consider this constraint while optimizing the configuration. Figure 20 finally shows the evolution of the constraints on the frequency and damping of the short period mode throughout the optimization process. According to reference (Ref. 21), the $\omega_s - \zeta_s$ diagram includes a region (the so-called fingerprint graph) identified as satisfactory by pilot opinion in terms of flying qualities. Within this region, the aircraft exhibits acceptable maneuverability (initial response) without being overly sensitive to control inputs, and with well-damped oscillations. It can be observed that the effect of the constraint during the optimization is to drive the aerodynamic and mass properties of the aircraft into the satisfactory region. The figure also includes a Design of Experiment analysis, which highlights the variability of the short period mode with respect to the design variables.

CONCLUSIONS

A multi-disciplinary analysis, trim, and optimization were carried out on the Clean Aviation HERA UCB configuration. This work focused on the extension of an aero-structural optimization framework with trim capabilities to the modelling of flying qualities constraints for the aircraft developed within the Clean Aviation HERA project. The MDO framework built around GEMSEO enabled modular integration of DUST models. The framework supported the generation of surrogate models trained using machine learning regression in the multi-disciplinary loop. A multi-fidelity optimisation is performed in that full-order and surrogate based optimisation is compared.

In particular, a complete DUST model of HERA was created and implemented in the MDO framework. The model was verified against a RANS solution obtained with the TAU solver (Ref. 14). The aerodynamic analysis showed that interactional aerodynamic effects can be exploited to optimize the DEP (Distributed Electric Propulsion) configuration. Subsequently, using the developed framework, trim analysis and aero-structural optimization of the configuration were performed. The optimization led to a configuration optimized in terms of aircraft range, by minimizing wing mass and maximizing aerodynamic efficiency. The results showed very good correlation between the surrogate model predictions and the

Figure 15. Extended Design Structure Matrix of the Optimization problem.

Figure 16. Slices of Surrogate models for the aerodynamic and stability discipline outputs. Training data (dependent on multiple variables), Surrogate data with fixed design variables, validation point with fixed design variables.

Figure 17. MDO final results, design variables and Objectives. Comparison between Baseline configuration, optimized with surrogate, and optimized without the surrogate.

Figure 18. Optimization results (a) Geometry (b) spanwise lift distribution comparison between baseline and optimized configuration.

Figure 19. Static margin constraint optimization history.

Figure 20. Short Period constraint on the finger-print short-period flying qualities graph.

time-marching simulation results. The methodology for implementing stability and flying qualities constraints was therefore verified, demonstrating its crucial value during design to ensure that the aircraft is maintain desired flight performance during the development process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement HERA (Hybrid-Electric Regional Architecture) n° 101102007. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CAJU. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible. The authors thank Jose Fernandez Montes for his valuable support in the integration of the structural sizing discipline and Sven Lanza Ferran for the feedback on the multidisciplinary design framework. Thanks to Daniela Gisele Francois from DLR for the support on the TAU setup.

Daniele Granata would like to thank the support by PNRR 118 – TDA, Cycle 39 – Transitions (Ministerial Decree 118/23), funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU, Mission 4 Component 1. CUP: D43C23002740001

COPYRIGHT STATEMENT

The authors confirm that they, and/or their company or organization, hold copyright on all of the original material included in this paper. The authors also confirm that they have obtained permission, from the copyright holder of any third party material included in this paper, to publish it as part of their paper. The authors confirm that they give permission, or have obtained permission from the copyright holder of this paper, for the publication and distribution of this paper as part of the ERF proceedings or as individual offprints from the proceedings and for inclusion in a freely accessible web-based repository.

REFERENCES

1. Joon W Lim. Fundamental investigation of proprotor and wing interactions in tiltrotor aircraft. In *Proceedings of the 75th Annual Vertical Flight Society Forum and Technology Display, Philadelphia, PA, USA*, pages 13–16, 2019.
2. Alberto Savino, Alessandro Cocco, Alex Zanotti, Vincenzo Muscarello, et al. Numerical investigation of wing-propeller aerodynamic interaction through a vortex particle-based aerodynamic solver. In *48th European Rotorcraft Forum (ERF 2022)*, pages 1–9. Curran, 2022.
3. Alex Zanotti, Luca Menini, Alberto Savino, Donato Grassi, and Luca Riccobene. Experimental investigation of wing-propeller aerodynamic interaction in evtol configurations. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 152:109348, 2024.
4. C. Niro, A. Savino, A. Cocco, and A. Zanotti. Mid-fidelity numerical approach for the investigation of wing-propeller aerodynamic interaction. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 108950, 2024.
5. Geng Qiao and George N Barakos. Aerodynamic study of wingtip-mounted propeller and distributed propulsion system. 2024.
6. Eric S Hendricks, Eliot Aretskin-Hariton, Daniel Ingraham, Justin S Gray, Sydney L Schnulo, Jeff Chin, Robert Falck, and Dustin Hall. Multidisciplinary optimization of an electric quadrotor urban air mobility aircraft. In *AIAA Aviation 2020 Forum*, page 3176, 2020.
7. Ö Petersson and F Daoud. *Multidisciplinary optimization of aircraft structures with respect to static and dynamic aeroelastic requirements*. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Luft-und Raumfahrt-Lilienthal-Oberth eV, 2012.
8. Anne Gazaix, François Gallard, Vincent Ambert, Damien Guénot, Maxime Hamadi, Stéphane Grihon, Patrick Sarouille, Thierry Y Druot, Joël Brézillon, Vincent Gachelin, et al. Industrial application of an advanced bi-level mdo formulation to aircraft engine pylon optimization. In *AIAA Aviation 2019 Forum*, page 3109, 2019.
9. Neal T Frink, Brett R Hiller, Patrick C Murphy, Kevin Cunningham, and Gautam H Shah. Investigation of reduced-order modeling for aircraft stability and control prediction. In *AIAA Scitech 2019 Forum*, page 0980, 2019.
10. Daniele Granata, Alberto Savino, and Alex Zanotti. Numerical evaluation of aircraft aerodynamic static and dynamic stability derivatives by a mid-fidelity approach. *Aerospace*, 11(3):213, 2024.
11. Politecnico di Milano. DUST, <https://www.dust.polimi.it/>.
12. GEMSEO Documentation. GEMSEO: Generic Engine for Multi-disciplinary Scenarios, Exploration, and Optimization <https://gemseo.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>.
13. Matteo Tugnoli, Davide Montagnani, Monica Syal, Giovanni Droandi, and Alex Zanotti. Mid-fidelity approach to aerodynamic simulations of unconventional vtol aircraft configurations. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 115:106804, 2021.
14. DLR. TAU, <https://www.dlr.de/en/as/research-and-transfer/software-solutions/aerodynamics/software-tau>.
15. Alberto Savino, Alessandro Cocco, Alex Zanotti, Matteo Tugnoli, Pierangelo Masarati, and Vincenzo Muscarello. Coupling mid-fidelity aerodynamics and multibody dynamics for the aeroelastic analysis of rotary-wing vehicles. *Energies*, 14(21):6979, 2021.
16. Blake B Hillier, Mark J Stock, and Adrin Gharakhani. Robust and corrected coefficients for the rotor-body-interaction body. *AIAA Journal*, 59(10):4281–4283, 2021.
17. Peter D. Gray. Neuralfoil - a neural network-based airfoil performance predictor. <https://github.com/peterdsharpe/AeroSandbox>, 2023.
18. A Mateo-Gabín, T. Wagenaar, Mancini S., et al. Analysis and optimization of a distributed propulsion system for a regional transport aircraft. In *9th European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering (ECCOMAS 2024)*, pages 1–13, 2024.
19. J. Fernández Montes. *Optimización de Parámetros de Ala Mediante Algoritmos Genéticos*. Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, 2015.
20. Marta A. Martín Jose Fernández Montes Sven A. Lanzan Ferran Andrés Mateo-Gabín, Simone Mancini and Tim Klaproth. An ai-enhanced multidisciplinary optimization framework for net-zero transport aircraft. In *AIAA 2025, Las Vegas*, pages 1–18, 2025.
21. Michael V Cook. *Flight dynamics principles: a linear systems approach to aircraft stability and control*. Butterworth-Heinemann, 2012.
22. Douglas C Montgomery. *Design and analysis of experiments*. John Wiley & sons, 2017.
23. B Omede, AM Grande, et al. Machine learning and numerical optimization of bio-inspired 3d-printable sandwich core cell. In *ICAS PROCEEDINGS*, pages 1–17. International Council of the Aeronautical Sciences, 2024.
24. Jianguang Fang, Guangyong Sun, Na Qiu, Nam H Kim, and Qing Li. On design optimization for structural crashworthiness and its state of the art. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 55:1091–1119, 2017.

25. Daniele Granata, Alberto Savino, and Alex Zanotti. Evaluation of a mid-fidelity approach for the calculation of tiltrotor aerodynamic stability derivatives in cruise flight conditions. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, page 110384, 2025.